

EXA4MIND

D3.1

Architecture of AQIS

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Abstract

One of the core objectives of the EXA4MIND project is enabling Extreme Data Analytics and Processing. To fulfil this objective, one of the major modules of the project is the **Advanced Querying and Indexing System (AQIS)**, the architecture of which is presented in this document. With the development of AQIS, we aim to provide a data query system having a uniform querying mechanism for varying data models. The system includes modular components to cope with complex data and variety of querying capabilities/languages over them.

Keywords

Unified data access; Query languages; NLQ; Indexing; Workflows; APIs; EXA4MIND Platform; Extreme Data Database

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Dissemination Levels

PU Public Public, fully open, e.g. website

SEN Sensitive Confidential to EXA4MIND project and Commission Services

Deliverable Types

R Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)

DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC Websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER Software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete (basic operations for persistent storage)
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DBMS	Database Management System
DoA	Description of Action
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
HPC	High Performance Computing
iRODS	Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (Xu et al. 2017)
LLM	Large Language Model
NL	Natural Language
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLQ	Natural Language Query
REST	Representational State Transfer (Fielding 2000)
SQL	Structured Query Language (Codd 1970)
WP	Work Package

Table of Partners

Short Name	Partner
IT4I@VSB	IT4Innovations at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava (IT4Innovations) https://www.it4i.cz/en
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities https://www.lrz.de/english/
METU	Middle East Technical University (METU) https://www.metu.edu.tr/
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab https://www.australo.org/
EURAXENT	Euraxent https://www.linkedin.com/company/euraxent/
CVUT	Czech Institute of Informatics, Robotics and Cybernetics at the Czech Technical University (CIIRC CTU) https://www.ciirc.cvut.cz/
VALEO	Valeo https://www.valeo.com/en/czech-republic/
TERRAVIEW	Terraview https://www.terraview.co/
ALTRNATIV	Altrnativ https://altrnativ.com/?lang=en
VALEO.AI	Valeo.ai https://www.valeo.com/en/valeo-ai/

Executive Summary

One of the core objectives of the EXA4MIND project is enabling Extreme Data Analytics and Processing. To achieve this objective, one of the main modules of the project is the Advanced Querying and Indexing System (AQIS), which is studied in Task 3.2 of Work Package 3. This deliverable presents the concept and motivation behind AQIS and describes the architecture designed to realise the concept.

With the development of AQIS, we aim to provide a data query system having a uniform querying mechanism for varying data models. Hence, AQIS includes a set of database access points. Another motivation behind AQIS is to enable EXA4MIND users to develop workflows/pipelines involving data access in the form of Apache Airflow workflows. This accommodates the need for the application cases to run complex pipelines, which retrieve, process and store data, which is a pattern already described in the field of Data Warehousing using the acronym ETL (Extract, Transform, Load). The pipelines consist of many steps, using different interfaces to retrieve and store the data and different compute resources to process them. They can also include data preprocessing tasks from Data Preprocessing Toolbox, whose first version has been available with Milestone MS8 (Initial Version of the Data Preprocessing Toolbox).

In addition to data access points and workflow/pipeline definition, the architecture also includes modules for data caching, to provide efficient management of already retrieved results, and inference, to support Natural Language (NL) based querying and searching on the databases.

The deliverable presents two sample basic pipelines to demonstrate the use of Airflow and the modules of AQIS. The first one is a Natural Language Query pipeline to provide NL-based querying on a SQL (relational) database. The second one is a preprocessing pipeline, which gets the data from a file and process it in two parallel branches. In one branch, the retrieved data is loaded to a database. In the pipeline, in parallel to database loading, another branch of tasks processes the data and sends it to a queue to be processed by another task or pipeline.

The initial version of the module and workflow implementations are available within the project codebase on the IT4I@VSB OpenCode GitLab instance.

The architecture of AQIS has been developed through a **collaborative effort** of **WP1, WP2** and **WP3**, as it is related with Extreme Data Databases (studied under WP2) and it is a core module of EXA4MIND Platform (studied under WP1 Architecture Co-design). The **requirements from Applications Cases** of **WP4, WP5** and **WP6** were important inputs to the design process.

1 Introduction

One of the core objectives of the EXA4MIND project is enabling Extreme Data Analytics and Processing, which is studied in WP3. To fulfil this objective, one of the major modules of the project is **Advanced Querying and Indexing System (AQIS)**, which is produced in Task 3.2.

With the development of AQIS, we aim to provide a data query system having a uniform querying mechanism for varying data models. The system includes modular components to cope with complex data and variety of querying capabilities/languages over them. Hence, AQIS provides a set of database access points. Another motivation behind AQIS is to enable EXA4MIND users to develop workflows/pipelines involving data access in the form of Apache Airflow (The Apache Software Foundation 2024) workflows. The pipelines can include data preprocessing tasks from the Data Pre-processing Toolbox, whose first version has been available with Milestone MS8 (Initial Version of the Data Preprocessing Toolbox).

The main motivation behind this approach is the need for the application cases to run complex pipelines which retrieve, process and store data, which is a pattern often described using the acronym ETL [Extract, Transform, Load, cf. e.g. Vassiliadis et al. (2003) and Simitsis, Skiadopoulos, and Vassiliadis (2023)]. The application cases may have pipelines that consist of many steps, using different interfaces to retrieve and store the data and different compute resources to process them. Most of the application case pipelines will vaguely resemble the process of query execution in a regular Database Management System (DBMS) (albeit on a higher level), where first the query is parsed, then it is scheduled for execution and the DBMS performs the necessary computing and I/O operations to execute the query.

The EXA4MIND project aims to build a platform capable of processing extreme amounts of data using a unified interface. Therefore, we opted to use one of the popular workflow and ETL orchestration tools, Apache Airflow, which is known to perform well and provide a unified way to describe such pipelines, execute them and track their execution parameters. We describe the intended usage of Airflow further below in the document.

In the rest of the document, we discuss all aspects of AQIS step by step as follows: In Section 2, the general architecture of the system is described. In Section 3, the components of the architecture are elaborated on. In Section 4, the use of Airflow in AQIS with Natural Language Query (NLQ) and preprocessing pipelines is discussed. Finally, the document is concluded in Section 5.

2 Overview of AQIS Architecture

AQIS aims to provide a layer facilitating data access in data processing, analytics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) processes to EXA4MIND users. The architecture design to fulfil this is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Main Architecture of AQIS (upper, yellow box), Connecting to the Database / Object Store / Storage Layer (lower, blue box).

In the figure, the upper yellow enclosed part constitutes the AQIS main body, consisting of various components. These components, the yellow boxes within the AQIS box, are “submodule groups” in the language of EXA4MIND release management (cf. Deliverable D1.2, EXA4MIND 2024).

One of the basic functionalities targeted in AQIS is to provide data access and querying as a part of a pipeline. A natural requirement at this point would be to support workflow definition capabilities. To this aim, AQIS is designed to work with a variety of workflow definition standards, languages and tools. In the initial version of the architecture implementation, workflows are realised with Apache Airflow. It is an open-source, python based platform to create, schedule and run workflows in the sense of Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) of single computational tasks. This capability of AQIS reflects in the **AQIS Query Workflow Definition** component.

As another functionality targeted in AQIS, a set of workflow templates for common set of data related operations are provided, including INSERTing¹ data to a database from another resource (such as a CSV file), SELECTing data from a database, UPDATIng or DELETIng data on the basis of the provided criteria. A workflow template can also be a natural language query pipeline to query a database in natural language. The workflow categories can be extended further with other data preprocessing and AI

¹With capitalisation in “INSERTing” etc., we refer to standard database operations as, e.g., available through SQL.

workflow templates to facilitate all relevant applications in EXA4MIND. This capability reflects in the **Workflow Catalogue** component in Figure 1.

In every system that includes data and databases, having a catalogue of database collections is an essential component. This applies in particular to AQIS, which is envisaged to facilitate complex queries for which also more than one data(base) backend is used to generate the response. In AQIS, the **Database Catalogue** module is thus designed to keep the metadata of the database collections available. The metadata includes the type of the database, address of the database, information on the content structure and the volume of the database. To provide a flexible data model for the metadata, using JSON objects is a viable solution. Therefore, the Database Catalogue itself can be a NoSQL database such as MongoDB (see e.g. Plugge, Hawkins, and Membrey 2010), Elasticsearch (see e.g. Gormley and Tong 2015) or its fork OpenSearch.

NLQ capability to be provided by AQIS constitutes one of the research focuses of the EXA4MIND project. Database querying traditionally needs significant knowledge of the database query language. Although SQL (Codd 1970) is a standard query language for relational data models, there is not a single standard database query language over other (so-called noSQL) databases. Hence, depending on the data storage environment, the query languages to be used vary. To overcome this complexity, AQIS is designed to accept natural language as a database querying language. This brings up the problem of translating from natural language (such as English) to a target database query language (such as SQL), which can be tackled by Inference Models (Large Language Models, LLM) fine-tuned for the target query language. To this purpose, it is planned to provide a set of Inference Models trained for translation to different database query languages. Currently, fine-tuned models are available for SQL and MQL (MongoDB Query Language). This capability of AQIS is encapsulated in the **Query Translation** component in Figure 1. The component includes inference providers (in the sense Airflow providers²), as well as fine-tuned Inference Models, which then can be called as a task of a workflow. For instance, an application may start the workflow with a query in natural language and the obtained data can be directed to an AI task for prediction. The Compute module of the EXA4MIND Platform (see EXA4MIND Platform architecture, Figure 2 further below) can optionally be used to call the LLM as an HPC job and thus offload the work to a HPC environment.

With EXA4MIND addressing Extreme Data collections, the data to be returned from a query may be large. At this point, caching is a useful mechanism to store the results temporarily for any repeating query. For such cases, AQIS shall include a Cache and make use of Caching protocols, which are compatible with the Caching mechanisms of the EXA4MIND Platform. This capability is represented as **Cache Support Module** in Figure 1.

Lastly, an important goal of AQIS is to provide a uniform way of data access. To this aim, the platform is designed to include a set of REST APIs (Fielding 2000) and other APIs (**Interface Layer**) such that the Access and Query providers and designed workflows can be called through a User Interface or within another external application.

²In Airflow DAGs, tasks are usually implemented as instances of so-called **operators**, and systematic collections of operators are called **providers**, as further discussed in Section 4

Figure 2: Architecture of the EXA4MIND Platform Around AQIS, as further described in D1.2 (EXA4MIND 2024).

The bottom part of Figure 1 shows the initial set of database management systems, object stores and storage systems (blue box, not part of AQIS) that access is provided to in EXA4MIND via the work of WP3 and WP2. This set is determined on the basis of the data storage requirements of the Application Cases. For instance, in Autonomous Driving Application Case, the basic type of data is image collection. Beside this, the application case involves JSON objects to store the features extracted from the images. Therefore it is decided to store the data in S3, Open Search and MongoDB. Similar decisions have been taken for the other Application Cases as well, depending on the nature of the data used and the performance comparisons. AQIS includes an access provider or a query provider (again meaning Airflow providers, see Section 4) for addressing all the data stores considered in the architecture (**Providers – Data System Adaptors** component).

The overall architecture of the EXA4MIND Platform is presented in Figure 2. In addition to the AQIS module, EXA4MIND includes additional components such as a Compute module (with *Data Movement* and *HPC/Cloud/AI Systems Access* functionalities) and Toolboxes. Although these modules are not part of the AQIS Architecture, they play an important role in running AQIS workflows, complementing the AQIS submodule instances. For example, a database query result can be transferred to another task through streaming or staging. When the query returns a large volume of data, then the streaming or staging submodule handles the data transfer without data loss or bottleneck problems. The EXA4MIND architecture as a whole, as shown in the figure, is further described in Deliverable D1.2 (EXA4MIND 2024).

3 Components of the AQIS Architecture

In this section, each of the components of AQIS is presented in more detail. Note that such an architectural component of AQIS corresponds to a “submodule group” in EXA4MIND release management (cf. Deliverable D1.2, EXA4MIND 2024). For instance, the Query Translation-Inference component comprises a set of submodules related with inference, such as inference models and their providers.

3.1 AQIS Query Workflow Definition

AQIS is designed to support workflow/pipelines that include data access and querying tasks. Hence it is designed to support workflow definition capabilities. A variety of workflow definition standards, languages and tools, including YAML (Ben-Kiki, Evans, and Net 2021), Common Workflow Language (CWL, see e.g. Chapman et al. 2016), TOSCA (see e.g. Brogi, Soldani, and Wang 2014), and Apache Airflow (The Apache Software Foundation 2024) can be used for this. In the initial version of the architecture implementation, Apache Airflow is used for expressing and running the workflows.

3.2 Interface Layer

Interface layer component is designed to provide a uniform way of access to AQIS. To this aim, the system is designed to include a set of REST APIs and APIs. Through these interfaces, data and query providers and designed workflows can be called through a User Interface or within another external application. As an example, natural language querying can be a step in an external workflow of the EXA4MIND user, then the external workflow calls the API designed for the NLQ pipeline in AQIS. Alternatively, it is possible to design a Web Interface to send NLQ and present the result. In such a case a REST API to the NLQ pipeline of AQIS can be used.

3.3 Database Catalogue

In data focused systems, such as data lakes, it is essential to have a database catalogue to provide an index to the accessible collection of databases. AQIS includes a Database Catalogue component following the same approach. This component keeps the metadata of the databases, including information such as the type of the database, the structure or the schema of the data, basic statistics such as the number of instances in the database. Additionally, the address of/pointer to the location of the database is also stored as a part of metadata. Such index information is useful in managing the collection, as well as, given a query, identifying which database to send it, when necessary. The index shall also enable queries across different databases and storage systems, where the response contains combined data from multiple systems.

3.4 Query Translation – Inference

Providing NL support for database querying is one of the popular research problems that are addressed with the aim to lower the barrier of query language knowledge. In the literature, there are studies proposing NLQ solutions for database languages, such as SQL (Fu et al. 2023), for multi-database environments (Chen et al. 2023), or different applications (Barbieri et al. 2023). Therefore, AQIS is also designed to provide NLQ functionality to facilitate database access for EXA4MIND applications.

The Query Translation - Inference component, responsible for addressing this, includes a collection of NLP models which are fine-tuned for Natural Language Querying tasks, i.e., given a query in natural language, for translating to the query language of the target database. The LLM submodules may vary depending on the database query language they are fine-tuned for (such as SQL, MQL, Open Search Query Language, etc.) or the base model that is fine-tuned (such as LLma-3, Mistral, etc.). Hence, depending on the target database and the base model, the preferred model can be called for inference. Besides the models, the component includes Airflow providers for launching the models and auxiliary components such as **Prompt_generation**.

Several essential design issues have been considered in the component design in order to warrant performance:

- ◆ The inference model should be efficiently deployed and called. We expect that HPC infrastructure will be used on handling the requirements of the model in more compute-intensive cases. To this end, it can be run through our HPC/Cloud Access provider (cf. Deliverable D1.2, EXA4MIND 2024) and exposed through an API for request handling.
- ◆ HPC infrastructure is used almost exclusively through batch schedulers. Special care must be taken to keep the compute nodes utilised with actual prompt inference and not by repeated model loading.
- ◆ Inference requests should be distributed across multiple compute nodes. To this aim, e.g. ZeroMQ (see e.g. Akgul 2013) is considered as a viable solution through its asynchronous message handling without a dedicated message broker. It is robust enough to be arbitrarily executed as part of a batch job.

3.5 Workflow Catalogue

One of the basic motivations and contributions of AQIS architecture is to provide abstraction for database access and data manipulation (Create, Read, Update, Delete – CRUD) operations, and to be able to perform these tasks in a data processing and AI pipeline. In this way, a user can perform database operations within a pipeline without dealing with the details of coding for database access.

Our Workflow Catalogue component refers to a collection of workflow templates for frequently needed pipelines involving data access and manipulation. These pipelines include standard database operations. Note that these basic operations implementation may vary depending on the type of database. The collection may include templates for a variety of pipeline types. In the initial design, we envisage

basic groups of templates for SELECT/INSERT/UPDATE/DELETE³ operations, data preprocessing pipelines and query inference pipelines. Some of the workflow templates that we consider to include are as follows:

- ◆ Populating a database from a data resource (such as a file),
- ◆ Inserting a data instance into a database,
- ◆ Deleting a data instance from a database,
- ◆ Updating a data instance in a database,
- ◆ Cleaning noise in a data collection,
- ◆ Filling in missing values in a collection,
- ◆ LLM inference pipeline generating a database-language query from natural language.

In Figure 1, in the Workflow Catalogue component box, a set of sample templates is presented. For instance, for INSERT, there are two different templates: The first one is a single task pipeline, which only calls, e.g., an iRODS (Xu et al. 2017) access provider (note that the blue node in the workflow template denotes an access to Database/Object Store/Storage Layer, which is also painted in blue in the figure). The second one shows a more complex INSERT pipeline, where data is transferred from iRODS to a database. In this workflow template, a set of tasks are called in sequence. Again note that the colours of the nodes denote the type of the task. As in the first workflow template, data system access operations are shown in blue, whereas data validation operations are shown as yellow nodes. Note that in Figure 2, data validation tools are represented in yellow, and preprocessing tools are drawn in green. Such correspondence is represented through using the same colours in the workflow template nodes. Hence, the second workflow's first node is an iRODS data access task, the second node is a data validation task, checking the data retrieved from iRODS, then the third node is a data preprocessing task, converting the format of the data for the target databases. In the last step of the workflow, there are two concurrent data access nodes, visualising that data retrieved from iRODS is stored in two different databases.

An EXA4MIND user can adapt a workflow template by setting the parameters properly and modifying the task sequence if needed, according to the needs of the application case. In Section 4 (below), we discuss the usage of Airflow in AQIS in some more depth, presenting two sample pipelines. They can be considered as the concrete pipeline instances obtained by adapting workflow templates provided in the Workflow Catalogue.

³With these operations, we allude to standard database operations as, e.g., available through SQL. However, in AQIS context, such operations may involve multiple data back-ends, natural-language querying or other internal complexity.

3.6 Providers - Data System Adaptors

AQIS needs to efficiently access data systems (with which we mean storage systems and database management systems) in the backend: It is meant to provide “flexible” access to the systems – in the sense that it may deliver data from multiple backends combined – but also unifies data access and makes it systematic. To meet the first goal, it makes combined usage of “index databases” and the necessary database backends from which data is retrieved, and puts an appropriate “business logic layer” above (Airflow workflows). For uniform and systematic data access, AQIS offers Airflow providers/operators to connect to each back-end system in the Extreme Data Database and to retrieve data from it. The provider collection has to support the standard database operations Create, Read, Update, and Delete (CRUD) backend per backend, and makes up the submodule group “Providers - Data System Adaptors”.

With the first release, AQIS includes – in this scope – the following submodules with Airflow providers for data system access:

- ◆ the PostgreSQL provider available for Airflow (Apache Software Foundation, Airflow Community 2024c) for which first a usage how-to and later a unified EXA4MIND-specific interface shall be delivered at a later point of time,
- ◆ an analogous MongoDB provider (Apache Software Foundation, Airflow Community 2024b),
- ◆ a provider for leveraging S3 object-storage backends via data transfer/access operators (Apache Software Foundation, Airflow Community 2024a),
- ◆ and an iRODS provider developed within EXA4MIND to leverage iRODS and EUDAT-B2SAFE as also used within the LEXIS Platform (Golasowski et al. 2022; Munke et al. 2022).

The following further providers are envisaged for inclusion in AQIS releases, for example:

- ◆ a vector database provider, depending on the first vector databases to be tested for utilisation in particular in WP5, and
- ◆ an HDF5 provider easing the access of components within HDF5 (see e.g. Folk et al. 2011) files.

3.7 Cache Support

Caching is a straightforward yet highly effective technique for any application where data generation demands significant resources or time. It proves particularly useful in scenarios where the same data might be needed multiple times (Barker 2016). Typically, data is obtained in two primary operations: (i) executing queries to databases or data requests to storage or (ii) and running complex applications, such as AI tasks. In both cases, caching can greatly enhance performance by storing the generated data for future use.

Caching proves beneficial in the following two scenarios:

- ◆ **Expensive Data Generation:** When data generation requires substantial computational effort or time, such as with complex calculations, data transformations, or querying large datasets, caching can save resources by storing the results of these operations.
- ◆ **Repeated Access:** If data is likely to be requested multiple times, caching ensures that the system does not need to reproduce the data each time, thereby saving processing time and resources.

The most effective caching strategy is in-memory caching. This method stores cached data in the system's RAM, which provides the fastest access. However, as the project focuses on handling extreme data volumes, a more sophisticated approach like hierarchical storage management (HSM) will be evaluated to provide optimal bandwidth for substantial data volumes. There are also specialised solutions:

- ◆ **Application-Level Caching:** The cache can be integrated into the application's memory space. Various programming languages and frameworks offer libraries for this purpose.
- ◆ **Database Caching:** Some DBMSs have built-in caching support. For example, MySQL's query caching stores the results of frequently executed queries (Schwartz, Zaitsev, and Tkachenko 2012).
- ◆ **Proximity Caching:** This approach involves storing data closer to the compute node to avoid network delays, such as edge caching or CDN (Content Delivery Network) caching for web applications.

Although there are various strategies, the most common caching workflow includes the following steps:

- ◆ **Cache Check:** Before executing a database query or running a computational task, the application first checks the cache to see if the data is already available. If the data is found in the cache, it is retrieved directly, avoiding re-execution.
- ◆ **Data Generation:** If the data is not found in the cache, the application proceeds to generate the data by executing the query or running the necessary task.
- ◆ **Cache Storage:** Once the data is generated, it is stored in the cache for future requests. This ensures that subsequent requests can be served quickly and efficiently.

In the EXA4MIND project, there are various applications that can benefit from caching. For example, in WP6 Agriculture Application Case, satellite images are retrieved and processed regularly. The same image can be used in different tasks and pipelines. For time and space efficiency, rather than directly retrieving the image, a cache check is performed to see whether the image is already available. The codes of the caching mechanism for our Agriculture Application Case, which constitute the initial version of the AQIS Cache Support component, are available within the project codebase on <https://opencode.it4i.eu>.

Another application case of EXA4MIND that may benefit from caching is the Molecular Simulations in WP4. The re-weighting calculations require retrieving the relevant simulation data. If the data is already retrieved for an earlier analysis, a cache check will be helpful to prevent retrieving the data redundantly, and thus to reduce the access cost.

4 Use of Airflow in AQIS and Sample Airflow Instances

The usage of the Apache Airflow in AQIS has been briefly described in the introductory section and previous sections. In this section, we will – after some words on Airflow itself – discuss example workflows/pipelines in AQIS as executed with Airflow.

Airflow is a popular tool for unified description and execution of complex chains of tasks, i.e. workflows, which are defined as DAGs in this context. A DAG is represented by a Python file containing definition of the individual vertices of the DAG - the tasks, their parameter values and relations between each other.

The Airflow then parses the DAG and offers a streamlined web-based UI and a REST API used to trigger their execution - the DAG run. The execution can be triggered either manually or based on a schedule or time pattern (“cron job”). A set of DAG parameters can be specified for each execution of a DAG. The parameters are stored in a database used by Airflow and can be retrieved back on demand. That way, the execution of each DAG is tracked in a unified way.

The tasks are usually represented as instances of **Airflow operators**, which are classes implementing the actual executable code. The parameters of such a task can be for example a SQL query, a path to a file, a number or other arbitrary values. A collection of **operators** related to a common service or API is called **provider**.

There is already a large number of **providers** available for many popular DBMS and other IT (Information Technology) systems controllable via APIs. Therefore, the core operations of AQIS can relatively easily be implemented as Airflow DAGs with defined set of parameters. These DAGs will be available through the workflow catalogue component.

The subsections below discuss two illustrative examples of pipelines for EXA4MIND executed via Airflow.

4.1 NLQ Pipeline

Natural Language Querying (NLQ) means interrogating a database using natural language (e.g. English) to facilitate access to data. The aim is to reduce the barrier of need for knowledge about a database querying language.

AQIS aims to provide NLQ as a service to the EXA4MIND users, which is realised via an Airflow instance. This section describes the development steps of the solution, using Apache’s Airflow infrastructure and a Large Language model (LLM) at the core.

Figure 3: NLQ Pipeline.

In the following subsections, firstly, the target database used in the pipeline is explained. Then each step of the Airflow workflow is described with references to the implementation.

4.1.1 Database

Spider (Yu et al. 2018), which is a context-independent dataset, is used as the sample target data. The target data consists of about 160 different databases. Having such a database is crucial to analyse the capabilities of the solution.

Within the project, the Spider databases are migrated from SQLite (see e.g. Gaffney et al. 2022) to PostgreSQL (Stonebraker and Rowe 1986). During the migration, the following type conversions are performed:

- ◆ YEAR, INT, MEDIUMINT, BIGINT typed columns in SQLite are mapped as BIGINT typed column in PostgreSQL.
- ◆ BLOB, TEXT, CHAR, VARCHAR typed columns in SQLite are mapped as TEXT typed columns.
- ◆ BIT, BOOLEAN, BOOL, SMALLINT, TINYINT typed columns in SQLite are mapped as SMALLINT typed columns.
- ◆ DATE, DATETIME, TIMESTAMP typed columns in SQLite are considered as TIMESTAMP typed columns.
- ◆ DOUBLE, REAL, DECIMAL, FLOAT, NUMERIC, NUMBER typed columns in SQLite are considered as DECIMAL typed columns.

After these conversions, multiple databases in the dataset are available for development.

4.1.2 Airflow-based Workflow Concept

Considering the NLQ task, the workflow has two inputs provided from the outside environment: a user query in English and the target database name. The visual representation of Airflow workflow steps is shown in Figure 3. As depicted in the figure, the workflow is composed of three consecutive tasks.

Step 1 - Query Processing. This step is responsible for preparing the LLM prompt for the database query generation step. Since the mere user query in English is not

enough to get satisfying results, LLM models should be informed about the table names, column names, and foreign keys alongside the user NL query. The migrated Spider databases are stationary, hence a set of engineered prompt templates can be prepared as a JSON file. When a new NL query is received, it is merged with the prompt template matching to the relevant database. The target database name and the prepared LLM prompt is shared with next steps via **xcom_push** calls. Note that, XComs (cross-communications) are a mechanism of Airflow for the tasks to talk to each other. They are variables associated per task instance, and they are designed for communication between tasks of the workflow. XComs are explicitly pushed and pulled to/from their storage using the `xcom_push` and `xcom_pull` methods for communication between tasks (The Apache Software Foundation 2024).

Step 2 - Database Query Generation. This step is responsible for loading the relevant LLM into memory, feeding the prompt read via **xcom_pull** calls to LLM, and generating the database query to execute in the next step. Different LLM models can be trained for the NLQ task. For our initial tests, as the LLM model, **deepseek-ai/deepseek-coder-6.7b-instruct** has been used. DeepSeek-coder (DeepSeek-AI et al. 2024) is an open-source LLM to solve coding tasks. This has been motivated by the fact that NL to database query conversion can be considered as a coding task. Once the LLM response is generated, the generated SQL query is passed to the next step via an **xcom_push** call.

Step 3 - Database Query Execution. This step is responsible for connecting to the database, running the generated SQL query and retrieving the results. After this step, the database query results can be presented to the user e.g. via an API response or a file-based output.

4.1.3 Concrete NLQ Workflow Example

Processing the Query. The first task of our AQIS pipeline is processing the input natural language query. Depending on the relevant target database, the AQIS system retrieves the respective prompt template. The prompt templates are stored in a JSON file in key/value format, where the prompt template for each database is retrieved from the file, and includes:

- ◆ a system prompt that describes the intended task,
- ◆ schema information that presents table names and column names,
- ◆ foreign key relationships that explain the relationships between the tables, and
- ◆ the natural language query written by the user.

Write only the SQL with no explanation for the query using the following schema. Do not select extra columns that are not explicitly requested.

```
Schema:
<table_1(column_1, column_2, ...)
<table_2(column_1 column_2, ...)
...
...
Foreign keys:
<table_1>.<column_1> = <table_2>.<column_2>
...
...
Question:
<NL question>
```

Figure 4: AQIS SQL Prompt Template.

A sample prompt template for SQL is given in Figure 4. Assume now, a user writes the following NL query and database:

What is the average, minimum, and maximum age of all singers from France?

Database: concert_singer

A prompt template similar to the example given in Figure 4 is selected for the **concert_singer** database, considering the information from the JSON file.

Generating the SQL Query. The second task of the AQIS pipeline is generating an SQL statement for the corresponding natural language query. For this purpose, the prompt template is filled (see Figure 5) with the query-specific information and fed to a large language model.

The language model is fine-tuned for the text-to-SQL task, using the exact prompt format during fine-tuning. Therefore, the model knows how to process the given prompt. As a result, the model generates the corresponding SQL statement:

```
SELECT avg(age), min(age), max(age) FROM singer WHERE country = 'France';
```

We tested this scenario utilising the Deepseek-coder-6.7b-instruct 1 model by the Deepseek AI team. AQIS was deployed on a local server with an i7-8700K CPU @ 3.70GHz, 12 cores, and 32 GB memory. The peak memory usage was approximately 29 GB, and the peak CPU usage corresponded to 7 busy CPU cores.

Executing the SQL Query. The final task within the NLQ Pipeline is then executing the generated SQL query on the selected database. For the sample query, the result set includes the following:

```
[(Decimal('34.5'), 25, 43)]
```

Write only the SQL with no explanation for the query using the following schema. Do not select extra columns and do not use 'AS' statements that are not explicitly requested.

Schema:

```
stadium(Stadium_ID, Location, Name, Capacity, Highest, Lowest, Average)
singer(Singer_ID, Name, Country, Song_Name, Song_release_year, Age, Is_male)
concert(concert_ID, concert_Name, Theme, Stadium_ID, Year)
singer_in_concert(concert_ID, Singer_ID)
```

Foreign keys:

```
concert.Stadium_ID = stadium.Stadium_ID
singer_in_concert.Singer_ID = singer.Singer_ID
singer_in_concert.concert_ID = concert.concert_ID
```

Question:

What is the average, minimum, and maximum age of all singers from France?

Figure 5: Prompt Template Adapted to **concert_singer** Database Query.

4.1.4 Implementation

The codes of the NLQ pipeline Airflow instance are available within the project code-base on <https://opencode.it4i.eu>.

4.2 Preprocessing Pipeline

Preprocessing is often an obligatory step of data processing, such as clearing out invalid data or changing the data format to a required structure before it is processed by a task. In order to handle such commonly and frequently used tasks, in EXA4MIND, the Data Preprocessing Toolbox of the project includes a variety of preprocessing tools. Although this toolbox is a standalone EXA4MIND module, a significant part of its usage will supposedly happen from AQIS.

To showcase this usage scenario, we present a sample preprocessing pipeline – a sample workflow, which uses preprocessing tasks in the toolbox. Our preprocessing tool to load the data from a CSV file to a PostgreSQL database is called CSV-to-Relational-DB conversion tool (cf. Deliverable D1.2, EXA4MIND 2024). In a parallel execution branch, the data is also processed and sent to a Kafka (Kreps, Narkhede, Rao, et al. 2011) queue (see below) to be processed further in another Airflow pipeline.

The visual representation of the pipeline is presented in Figure 6. In the rest of this section, the steps of the pipeline are described.

4.2.1 CSV to Relational DB Conversion Tool

The workflow discussed here is crafted to accept files in Apache Parquet format or Comma Separated Values (CSV) files, process them and insert them into PostgreSQL database. We can demonstrate the pipeline applying it to Parquet files of viticulture data, from the WP6 Agriculture Application Case. In the CSV-to-Relational-DB

Figure 6: Data Type Conversion and Preprocessing Pipeline.

conversion tool, as the first Airflow task (**consume_parquet**), a Parquet file can be processed to obtain a CSV file. Then, as second task (**create_table**, the core CSV-to-Relational-DB task), an SQL table is created and filled with the data from the CSV file. In the current version of the preprocessing tool, the structure of the SQL table that will be populated is assumed to be known, and is not inferred from the input Parquet/CSV file. The module is implemented in Python and relies on the “psycopg” (Varrazzo et al. 2024) PostgreSQL adaptor.

4.2.2 Stream Processing / Kafka Producer Tasks

In the parallel branch of the preprocessing pipeline, upon completion of the first task, i.e., extraction of the CSV content from the Parquet file, the **consume_csv** task processes the CSV content and creates average values for a certain granularity (the input file contains weather temperatures; hence daily temperature averages are obtained). We have designed this task with the intention of a further stream-based data processing via Apache Kafka (Kreps, Narkhede, Rao, et al. 2011).

Apache Kafka is an event streaming platform, operating with a publisher/subscriber architecture. Kafka allows events, or messages to be filed under topics, which publishers can write under and subscribers can read from. This is done through streams, and Kafka has fault-tolerance guarantees. Kafka can thus be used to store the results of a processing task or to start more tasks with stream input coming from Kafka.

As the CSV data is processed, the **send_to_kafka** task is triggered. This task emits the data ingested in the previous task to Kafka, ready to be consumed by clients subscribed to the topic.

At this stage, the Parquet/CSV file provided has been sent to Kafka for immediate processing, while also having been stored (see above) at the beginning of the pipeline to a database for longer-term storage.

4.2.3 Implementation

The codes of the preprocessing pipeline Airflow instance are available within the project codebase on <https://opencode.it4i.eu>.

5 Conclusion

This document has described the architecture of AQIS, which provides a layer to facilitate the data access needs of EXA4MIND users. Use of DBMS is an indispensable part of every computation involving extreme data. However, the high variety in the nature of data used in applications in different scenarios, and the need for technical knowledge on varying database query languages bring complications and constitute a barrier for data access. With AQIS, we aim to make efficient data access easier by

- ◆ providing uniform data access points for a variety of database management systems and storage systems,
- ◆ supporting workflow definitions that involve data access and data preprocessing, and
- ◆ providing Natural Language Querying mechanism to overcome the barrier of learning a query language.

Furthermore, AQIS uses caching, staging, and high-performance computing capabilities of the EXA4MIND architecture for efficient and seamless use and transfer of the database query results within Airflow pipelines.

This initial version of the AQIS architecture is modular and thus open to further conceptual improvement and to feature enhancements such as the design of more Airflow pipeline templates.

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